

THE MAJOR FACTORS INFLUENCING ON CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ON ADVANCE OF A CAREER LADDER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195467>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to research of factors which are capable of influencing the development of career and career growth as a whole. The process of a human choice in professional activity, proceeding from its personal and business qualities and abilities is considered in this article. Also the purpose of this article is to concretize and define the major factors promoting advancement of a career ladder, and also to draw a conclusion about those conditions that influence on development of career most effectively.*

Key words: *career; structure of career; purposes; choice; career anchor; external factors; internal factors.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА РАЗВИТИЕ КАРЬЕРЫ И ПРОДВИЖЕНИЕ ПО КАРЬЕРНОЙ ЛЕСТНИЦЕ

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена исследованию факторов, которые способны повлиять на развитие карьеры и карьерный рост в целом.*

В статье рассматривается процесс выбора человека в профессиональной деятельности исходя из его личных и деловых качеств и способностей. Также целью данной статьи является конкретизировать и определить основные факторы, способствующие продвижению по карьерной лестнице, а также сделать вывод о тех условиях, которые влияют на развитие карьеры наиболее эффективно.

Ключевые слова: *карьера; структура карьеры; цели; выбор; карьерный ведущий; внешние факторы; внутренние факторы.*

In the process of professional activity, a person always makes a choice. When applying for a job, he sets certain goals for himself. The organization, in turn, when hiring him, also pursues its own specific goals. To do this, the applicant for the position must realistically assess his professional and business qualities and correlate them with the requirements that the organization sets for him. Both his success in getting a job and the success of his entire career as a whole depend on this.

A person's needs, life and career goals vary across time periods. Each person to some extent plans his career, his future, focusing on needs, abilities, a real assessment of the existing socio-economic conditions for the realization of his expectations. An integral part of personnel management is assisting an employee in realizing his life goals as an important condition for motivating his behavior in work.

Career planning for an employee is the organization of his advancement through the stages of job and qualification growth, helping him to develop and implement professional knowledge and skills in the interests of the company.

A professional career is an important incentive for the improvement of a specialist.

In particular, as noted in the literature [1], career goals are to:

- the position held corresponded to the individual's self-esteem and provided moral satisfaction;
- the work was located in an area whose natural conditions have a beneficial effect on health and allow for good rest;
- working conditions enhanced human capabilities and developed them;
- the work was well paid or there would be an opportunity to receive large additional incomes;
- work made it possible to continue active education, raise children and housework, etc.

The term "career" itself can reflect both the dynamic, developing over time, and the static side of the concept. For example, images of a career path, a career ladder refer to the dynamic side of this concept, and the scientific construct identified by E. Shane "Career anchors" seem to be a stable static mechanism, which reflects the essence of the phenomenon being described.

According to E.G. Moll, career development can be influenced by situational, institutionalized and individual factors of personality development [6].

American specialist Edgar Schein developed the concept of "Career Anchors". He asserts the need to determine one's "career anchor" - an interest or value that a person will never give up if he has to make a choice [2].

Shane identified the following "career anchors":

1) People with a career anchor "professional com" "petence" want to be masters of their craft, they are especially happy when they achieve success in the professional field, but quickly lose interest in work that does not allow them to develop their abilities.

2) People with the "managerial competence" anchor demonstrate a great desire to become managers, managers; their experience suggests that they possess the skills necessary to achieve the top level of general management.

3) People with a career anchor of "creativity and initiative" feel the need to build or create something, completely belonging to them, which will reflect their dignity. Usually such people become entrepreneurs.

4) The main need for people with the anchor "autonomy and independence" is to be independent, free from all the connections that arise when working in large organizations. Promotions, transfers and salaries make them dependent on others.

5) People with the "stability" anchor are interested in long-term reliability and stable performance. There is an anchor of job stability and an anchor of residence stability. In the first case, a person applies for a job in an organization that provides a certain length of service, has a good reputation, appears more reliable in its industry, and shifts the responsibility for career management to the employer. He will make any geographical movements if the company requires it. And in the second, a person associates himself with a geographic region and changes jobs or organizations, if this is not accompanied by a sudden move.

6) Integration of lifestyles as a career anchor. A person is focused on the integration of various aspects of life. He wants family, career and self-development to be balanced in his life. Such a person values his life in general more - where he lives, how he improves - than a specific job or career.

7) The main value of the career anchor “challenge” is competition, victory over others, overcoming obstacles, solving difficult problems. The person is “challenge” oriented.

8) The values of the “service” anchor are “working with people,” “helping people,” “the desire to make the world a better place,” etc. A person with such an anchor will not work in an organization that is hostile to his goals and values, and will refuse promotion or transfer to another job if this does not allow him to realize the main values of life.

Career management activities contain a number of management actions carried out by management subjects, each of which pursues its own interests. The best option is achieved when a compromise of these interests is achieved.

In the process of forming a system for managing the business career of personnel, it is necessary to take into account that a career is the interaction of three groups of factors:

1. the personality of the person himself;
2. the professional environment in which a person works and develops;
3. non-working environment in which he lives and rests [4]. Let's analyze the factors influencing career growth and in general on the career itself as a whole. There are external and internal factors: We can conditionally divide external factors of career development into two areas: general (non-official) and special (official). This division is conditional, since factors operating in the non-work sphere form many characteristics of an employee that have career significance, and, conversely, official position largely determines his attitude, behavior, connections in the family and society. Let's look at the table of external career factors.

Here is an example of a well-known form of career planning in Japan, called the lifetime employment system, which has proven its viability and effectiveness. Having received an education, a person goes to work for a company and works there until retirement, mentally associating himself directly with the company and understanding that his personal prosperity depends on the prosperity of his company. The system creates confidence in the future; the employee is almost guaranteed against dismissal. But the lifetime employment system in Japan applies only to 25-30% of workers in large companies, and layoffs are still possible if the company's financial situation worsens [5].

External factors of career development

General sphere (non-official) Special sphere (official)

1. Family. Family can be a source of career energy in the service, or it can also be a dampener. If for a family service is a clan tradition, a source of satisfaction of material and social needs, it supports the employee's career, is proud of his achievements, and creates a favorable environment at home for working on himself. 1. Organizational structure. The structure of the organization determines job models; professional requirements for a specialist; a list of functions that a professional in a certain position must perform; opportunities for professional and job growth.

2. Close circle of the employee and his family. It develops on the basis of constant relationships with childhood friends, studies, and the first stages of service. These relationships are cemented common interests and similarity of career goals. Recognition by this environment of a person's achievements is a significant incentive for his further advancement. 2. Personnel policy of the organization. The organization's philosophy regarding young professionals; chances of

getting a higher position; whether conditions for training, advanced training or retraining are created; is it possible to reduce the position and why? What is the remuneration system in the organization?

3. Macroenvironment: global community. Homeland, city, village where a person lives. A full-fledged stable career will not happen if you do not keep abreast of international events, neglect the history of the Fatherland, be indifferent to the fate of your country, and support anti-social political movements. 3. Social and legal norms of activity.

4. Social norms, culture, economic standard of living, technological development, politics, the nature of social relations. It is necessary to constantly monitor technical innovations, to catch in the achievements of science and practice what can enrich professional experience and personal way of activity. 4. Working conditions. Work and rest schedule, medical care for personnel; length of the working day and week; opportunities to receive social benefits; availability of overtime work; availability of business trips and their duration, etc.

5. Knowledge of the life of the business world is the basis for organizing your service in accordance with the changes occurring in it. 5. Principles of personnel promotion. Requirements for employee qualifications at each stage of professional and job advancement.

Analysis of internal factors influencing career development allows you to check your internal readiness for future professional activities and outline ways for further professional and personal development:

1. Human ability factor. The simplest and surest way to identify your abilities is to analyze your experience and find out what you are most successful at. It is advisable to begin this analysis by identifying the activities that give you the most pleasure. However, activity is always associated with solving problems, many of which do not correspond to the sphere of personal interests. The internal resource can be activated in two ways. The first is mastering what is not interesting: in the process of increasing knowledge about the subject of activity, the ability to handle it, it becomes "own" and interesting. The second way is to involve the will in unwanted but necessary activities.

2. The factor of the ability to awaken, maintain and develop activity in solving professional problems and advancing in professional skills. This ability is closely related to a person's temperament. When planning a career, a differentiated orientation to the type of temperament is necessary.

3. Factor of self-confidence, desire for leadership, sense of duty and responsibility. There is a danger that confidence can transform into self-confidence, the desire for leadership degenerates into lust for power and vanity, which can deform career process with a focus on selfish goals. At the same time, the dominance in the personality structure of the qualities of a sense of duty and responsibility fetters initiative, creativity, and generates uncertainty and fear for the consequences of decisions made.

4. Factor of professional knowledge and experience. In each area of professional activity the set of these components is specific. But all of them are determined by the qualification requirements for the position and acquired specialty. Even more important for a successful career is an orientation towards the demands that professional life makes today and will make tomorrow. (Analysis of this factor is carried out according to any of the possible lists of qualification requirements).

5. Factor of interest and ability to learn and gain experience. Abilities develop through activity, so self-development of abilities lies in constantly achieving new milestones. Interest has an amazing ability - not to disappear after successfully achieving a goal, but, on the contrary, to intensify.

6. Health factor. The relationship between health and career is very significant. Any advancement of a person is associated with stress on the body, since in connection with this there is a tension of protective forces, the mobilization of bodily and neuropsychic resources to adapt to changes and solve life problems. In this regard, it is necessary to have certain anti-stress programs [6].

Despite this, some studies show that often a busy and interesting active life contributes to the fact that psychosomatic diseases do not develop, but rather are cured.

The employee's satisfaction with his professional destiny and personal life, as well as his labor productivity, which directly affects the efficiency of the organization, depends on how correctly the career path is chosen and implemented.

So, career development occurs effectively only when a person makes maximum use of internal resources and takes into account possible influence of external factors of professional advancement towards the intended goal. A person's internal resources determine his way of achieving this goal. However, it is necessary to know and take into account the influence of career growth factors on a person, and then career advancement will be successful.

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